

Studies on Solutions of High Dielectric Constant. Part IV. Solvation of Some Ions in Protic and Aprotic Solvents from Conductance Data

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A comparative study of solvation of ions in some protic and aprotic solvents has been made from conductance data, using the correction suggested by Robinson and Stokes¹ for non-applicability of the Stokes' law to small particles of common ionic dimensions. The results indicate that ions, in general, are more solvated in protic than in aprotic solvents, suggesting the important role of protons in enhancing the solvation of ions, more especially of anions, the cations being solvated by ion-dipole interactions. Further, appreciable solvation of ions is indicated in liquid HCN, a conclusion similar to that of Coates and Taylor² but opposed to the views of Audrieth and Kleinberg³.

The study of solvation of ions in non-aqueous solvents has been more or less neglected until quite recently. The difficulties of such a venture have been admirably summarised by Robinson and Stokes¹. The problem has attracted the attention of some workers⁴⁻⁶ recently. Conductance data have been utilised by some investigators to estimate the solvation numbers of ions in some solvents^{1,2,3,7}. None of them appears to have made the corrections, suggested by Robinson and Stokes¹, for the non-applicability of the classical Stokes' law to particles of common ionic dimensions. Overlooking of this correction has led some workers to assume inapplicability of Stokes' law to some larger ions like K^+ , Rb^+ , Cs^+ , Cl^- , Br^- , and ClO_3^- , but at the same time accepting its applicability to smaller ions⁸ like Li^+ and Na^+ . This correction is therefore necessary for estimating the correct size of moving ionic units (with the solvation envelope) during the transport of ions in electrical conductance. The above anomaly disappears altogether only when this correction is made. Solvation of some ions in a few protic and aprotic solvents has been examined from this point of view in this communication.

Method.—The details of the method and the ideas on which it is based have been described by Robinson and Stokes¹ and hence have been omitted here except for some explanatory remarks. According to Stokes' law, radius r_s of an ion is given by:

$$r_s = \frac{0.92|Z|}{\lambda_\infty \eta_0} \quad (1)$$

The terms used have their usual significance. The r_s value for the tetra-alkylammonium

1. "Electrolyte Solutions", Butterworths Publications, London, 1961, pp. 62-63, 125.
2. Bockris and Conway, "Modern Aspects of Electrochemistry", Butterworths Publications, London, 1954, pp. 47, 63.
3. Bockris, *Quart. Rev.*, 1949, 3, 173.
4. Parker, *ibid.*, 1962, 16, 163.
5. Miller and Parker, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 117.
6. Looy and Hammett, *ibid.*, 1959, 81, 3872.
7. Hartley and Raikes, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, 23, 393.

ions, assumed to be unsolvated due to their large size and small surface charge and to which the classical Stokes law is expected to apply, turns out to be smaller than the respective crystallographic radius, r_c , of the ion in question. One would, however, expect that r_s in equation (1) to be equal to r_c since the ion is unsolvated. Clearly, the constant factor in equation (1) and of the classical Stokes law, from which it is obtained, need to be multiplied by r_c/r_s in order that the equation may provide the correct value of the tetra-alkylammonium ion. These correction factors for the various tetra-alkylammonium ions may be plotted against r_s and from the graph the correction factor, r/r_s (r being the actual radius of the ion in solution), for various ions, supposed to be solvated and for which r_s can be obtained from (1), can be read (see Fig. 6.1, p. 125, ref. 1). Thus the corrected radius R_s ($=r$) of the solvated ion is given by

$$R_s = \frac{0.82/Z}{\lambda_0 \eta_0} \times \frac{r}{r_s} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Hence the volume V_s of the solvated ion is $4/3 \pi R_s^3$ and not $4/3 \pi r_s^3$, as has been assumed by other workers hitherto. If one disregards the contraction of the solvent due to electrostriction*, the approximate solvation number 'n' can be calculated from the volume of the solvent molecule. The volume of the ion itself may be neglected in most cases. One can thus have an approximate idea of the number of molecules of the solvent associated with different ions.

The values of λ_0^{**} for different ions in a number of solvents have been collected from the literature⁷⁻¹⁰. Further, assuming that the tetra-alkylammonium ions are unsolvated in different solvents (i.e., $\lambda_0 \eta_0 = \text{constant}^\dagger$ and is independent of temperature and solvent), approximate solvation numbers of different solvated ions in a number of solvents have been calculated by the procedure outlined above and the results thus obtained are summarised in Table I.

DISCUSSION

Table I shows that solvation of anions in protic solvents like water, methanol, ethanol, etc. is appreciably higher than that in aprotic solvents like nitrobenzene, pyridine, dimethylacetamide, etc., in which protons are not available. This indicates the role of protons in enhancing the solvation of anions, as has already been recognised by other workers⁴, by forming some sort of hydrogen bond between the ions and the solvent molecules. This would result in a little higher tendency for solvation in anions than in cations of the same size. This is shown by the higher solvation number of F^- as compared to that of K^+ of the same radius in solvents like water and methanol, etc.

*This effect may be appreciable for smaller ions.

** λ_0 for different ions, except in water, MeOH, EtOH, and formamide, are not accurate due to lack of transference number data in other solvents.

†The general applicability of this relation has been questioned by some workers; for example see Kraus, *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1949, **51**, 789. All the same, Walden's rule still remains a good guide for conductance studies in non-aqueous solvents.

6. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 1245.

9. Burgess and Kraus, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 706.

10. Witschonke and Kraus, *ibid.*, 1947, **69**, 2472, 2481.

TABLE I

Solvation numbers of some ions in various solvents from conductance data at 25°.

Ion.	Water.*	MeOH.	EtOH.	Liquid HCN.**	Forma- mide.‡	Methyl for- mamide.‡	Dimethyl- formi- mide.‡	Dimethyl- acet- amide.‡	Nitro- benzene.‡	Pyridi- ne.‡	Acetone.‡	Dimethyl sulphoxide.‡
Li†	7.0	5.0	5.8	4.3	4.7	..	3.0	..	..	2.5	2.7	..
Na†	4.7	4.6	3.8	4.3	3.5	3.5	2.4	2.1	1.6	2.4	2.6	2.4
K†	2.1	3.9	3.3	3.9	2.4	3.4	2.4	2.1	1.4	2.1	2.5	2.4
Rb†	1.8	3.7	3.1	3.8	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..
Cs†	1.8	3.3	2.9	3.7	..	3.0	..	..	..	..	..	..
NH ₄ †	2.1	3.7	3.7	..	2.0	..	..	..	1.4	1.2	2.2	..
Cs‡	9.6	8.0	..	..	6.4	..	..	..	..	..	..	..
Br-†	9.7	6.0	..	..	7.5	..	..	..	..	..	..	..
Ba‡	9.1	7.9	..	..	6.3	..	..	..	..	..	..	..
F-	3.8	5.0	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	2.4	..
Cl-	1.9	4.1	3.0	2.3	1.3	1.3	1.1	..	1.0	..	2.0	..
Br-	1.8	3.8	2.9	2.3	..	1.2	1.2	1.1	1.1	1.0	1.8	1.1
I-	1.8	3.4	3.4	2.6	1.4	1.1	1.3	1.2	1.2	1.1	1.8	1.1
NO ₂ -	2.0	3.4	2.7	2.5	1.2	1.1	1.1	1.0	1.0	1.0	..	..
ClO ₄ -	2.5	2.8	2.1	2.6	..	2.1	1.3	1.2	1.1	1.2	..	..
Fluorates-	6.6	4.5	2.8	4.1	..	..	2.0	1.7	2.7	2.0	2.4	1.9
CNS-	..	8.4	2.8	2.4	..	..	1.0	1.0	..	..	1.6	0.7

* Water is included in this table in order to present a comparative general picture of solvation in different solvents.

** Values of conductance in liquid HCN are at 18°.

† The values of ionic conductance in these solvents are not accurately known due to complete absence of transference number data. Ionic conductance has been mostly obtained by other workers either by making some arbitrary but reasonable division of electrolytic conductance of a suitable electrolyte into respective ionic contributions or by the application of Walden's rule, the latter method being used by us in some solvents. Hence accuracy of solvation numbers of different ions in these solvents is very much limited.

Solvation of cations is appreciable both in protic as well as in aprotic solvents with some higher tendency for solvation in the former although the data for the latter solvents are so meagre that no definite conclusion can be drawn. In view of the similar charge on the cations and the proton, the latter cannot induce higher solvation in cations. The obvious conclusion is that the solvent dipoles attach themselves to the cations with the negative pole towards the ion and according to Parker⁴, the cations are solvated on account of the "negative charge localised on the bare oxygen atom" which points towards the cation. The protons could have, at the most, a very secondary role in the solvation of cations.

As a proton-donor HCN should promote solvation of anions and as a dipolar molecule, of the cations. The results recorded in Table I confirm these deductions which are also supported by the work of Coates and Taylor⁵. These results are rather surprising on account of large ionic mobilities in liquid HCN, a fact that has led Audrieth and Kleinberg¹¹ to expect very little solvation (see also ref. 1, p., 164). Further work on HCN solutions is necessary to settle this question (ref. 1, p. 169).

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received January 6, 1963.